

Conclusion: This device can be used in the airport operational area to disperse birds away without affecting its health. The infrasound generating device will be cost effective, simple in construction, easy maintenance and more robust when compared to the dispersal techniques adopted in the airport nowadays.

Keywords: Bird strike, Infrasound, bird disperse, Airport operational area.

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DISHA – A DEVICE FOR AIDED EVACUATION FROM SMOKE-FILLED ENTRIES

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Purpose: Aided evacuation is an essential requirement after an incidence of fire in a constricted work place, public utility place and underground mines. The decision-making capability is subsided due to unavailability of human senses under such condition. It is a stated fact that senses are physiological capacity of organisms that provide data for perception. Humans have a multitude of senses but commonly known or recognised basic five senses are sight (ophthalmoception), hearing (audioception), taste (gustaoception), smell (olfaoception or olfactoception), and touch (tactioception). None of these are available to aid under an escape route or entry if the entry is filled with smoke / dust. The known prior art on the subject since 1882 is limited to application of plurality of fructoconical tactile material mounted on wire rope, both having reflective surfaces, which is secured at waste-line on designated escape routes. Such an application has severe limitations and activation of only ophthalmoception sense is the one inter-alia others.

Methods: Considering the limitations of the prior art on the subject a device DISHA is designed and developed which is acronym for 'Directional Illuminated Support Under Harsh Ambience'. DISHA is self-power contained device which can be used in underground mines, constricted work places and public utility places where designated escape way is essentially required. This device, DISHA, make available of two senses, namely – ophthalmoception sense and audioception sense. This boost survival chance of the trapped personnel.

Results: This improved aided evacuation device, DISHA, consists plurality of hollow cones mounted on a wire rope suitably secured at specified distance on waistline height on the designated escape route. The cones consist of an electronic circuit that stimulates the human sight and hearing senses thereby enabling trapped personnel to take better decision and safely evacuate from the hazardous area. The circuit of the cone consists of the push button, Timer IC, Capacitors, Resistors, Battery, voltage regulator as level shifter, relay driver IC, flasher and potentiometer. The push button activates laser light and alarm through self-power contained electronic circuit once the trapped personnel glides his hand on the slant side of the cone. The laser lights illuminate the path of the escape so that the trapped miner can see the direction of escape. The laser light is used so as the light gets least dispersal in a smoke-filled escape way / passage way. The alarm system notifies trapped personnel on other routes so that they can reach to the designated escape route or ask for assistance.

Conclusion: An aided evacuation system for emergency egress from smoke filled designated entries have been developed which boost survival chances of trapped personnel under such hazardous incidence occurred in constricted work places.

Keywords: Aided evacuation, smoke-filled entries, emergency escape, underground coal mining.